

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Therapeutic Potential of Moringa Extracts in Gout Management: A Comprehensive Review of Mechanisms, Formulations, and Future Prospects

Talele Urvasha*, Kundhiya Sandhya, Patel Krishna, Patel Sakshi, Nagar Janvi, Falaq Jujara, Jaswandi Mehetre, Vimal Kumar

School of Pharmacy, ITM SLS Baroda University

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 1 Jan 2026

Keywords:

Gout, Moringa oleifera, Hyperuricemia, Xanthine oxidase, formulation strategies

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.18115498

ABSTRACT

Gout is a metabolic disorder characterized by hyperuricemia and recurrent inflammatory arthritis due to monosodium urate crystal deposition in the joints. Conventional pharmacological therapies, such as nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, colchicine, and xanthine oxidase inhibitors, are effective but are often associated with adverse effects during long-term use. Consequently, there has been an increased interest in plant-based therapeutic alternatives with improved safety profiles. Moringa oleifera, commonly known as the drumstick tree, is a medicinal plant rich in bioactive phytochemicals, including flavonoids, phenolic acids, and antioxidants. Several studies have demonstrated its potential antihyperuricemic activity through the inhibition of xanthine oxidase, regulation of renal urate transporters, and anti-inflammatory effects mediated by the modulation of pathways such as NF- κ B and pro-inflammatory cytokines. This review summarizes the pathophysiology of gout, limitations of current therapies, pharmacological properties of Moringa oleifera, and various formulation strategies reported in the literature, including oral, topical, and advanced nano delivery systems. This review highlights the therapeutic potential of Moringa oleifera as a multi-mechanistic natural agent for gout management and emphasizes the need for further clinical studies and formulation optimization.

INTRODUCTION

Gout is a metabolic disorder primarily caused by excess uric acid in the body (hyperuricemia), which may arise from genetic, metabolic, and

environmental factors [1]. Uric acid is the final oxidation product of purine catabolism and is produced in the liver by the xanthine oxidase. In the kidneys, uric acid is excreted and reabsorbed through transporters such as urate transporter 1

*Corresponding Author: Talele Urvasha

Address: School of Pharmacy, ITM SLS Baroda University.

Email ✉: urvashakishor4@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

(URAT1), glucose transporter 9 (GLUT9), and ATP-binding cassette superfamily G member 2 (ABCG2) [2].

When uric acid levels become excessively high, they reach saturation and precipitate in cooler areas of the body, particularly near the joints, leading to the formation of monosodium urate (MSU) crystals, which are the primary cause of gout [3]. Acute gout is characterized by severe pain and inflammation of the affected joints and surrounding tissues. The metatarsophalangeal joint is the most commonly affected joint, accounting for approximately 56–78% of all cases. However, gout may also involve other joints, such as the midfoot, ankle, and upper limb joints [4].

Chronic gout develops after repeated acute attacks over several years and is associated with persistent pain, joint stiffness, progressive joint destruction, and tissue damage. It is further characterized by

the presence of tophi, aggregates of MSU crystals and dead immune cells [1].

The most commonly used synthetic drug for the treatment of gout is allopurinol, which reduces uric acid formation by inhibiting the xanthine oxidase enzyme. Despite its effectiveness, allopurinol is associated with adverse effects on the skin, gastrointestinal tract, and other organ systems. Due to these side effects, there is increasing interest in screening natural medicines as safer alternatives for the treatment of gout [5].

Current Treatment available for Gout

Currently, synthetic drugs are commonly used for the management of gout. These agents primarily aim to reduce inflammation during acute attacks and to control uric acid levels in the body. The mechanisms of action and associated side effects of commonly used drugs for acute gout are summarized in Table 1 [5,6].

Table 1: Drugs used for Acute Gout

Drug Class	Examples	Mechanism of Action	Common/ Key Side Effects
Nonsteroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs)	Indomethacin, Naproxen	They inhibit	Gastrointestinal upset
Colchicine	Colchicine	It disrupts	Diarrhea, nausea, vomiting,
Glucocorticoids	Prednisolone, Triamcinolone	It exerts	Short-term use may cause elevated blood glucose levels, mood changes, and fluid retention. Long-term use

Table 2: Drugs for Chronic Gout

Drug Class	Examples	Mechanism of Action	Common/ Key Side Effects
Uric Acid Synthesis Inhibitors	Allopurinol, Febuxostat	It inhibits	Allopurinol:
Uricosuric Drugs	Probenecid	It increases	Mild gastrointestinal irritation, headache, dizziness, and risk of renal stone formation (requires high fluid intake).
Urate Oxidase (Uricase) Analogues	Pegloticase	Enzyme that oxidizes uric acid to allantoin, a more soluble compound	Infusion reactions (anaphylaxis, hives, chest pain, shortness of breath), gout flares, nausea, and vomiting

Moringa Oleifera:

Moringa oleifera, commonly known as the drumstick tree, is a drought-tolerant plant

belonging to the family Moringaceae and is widely distributed across India, Africa, and other tropical and arid regions. It has been traditionally used for both nutritional and medicinal purposes [7]. *Moringa oleifera*, often referred to as the “Miracle Tree” or “Tree of Life,” provides significant health, nutritional, and ecological benefits. Almost every part of the plant has documented food, medicinal, industrial and domestic applications [8,9].

Among the various plant parts, leaves are particularly valuable. They can be consumed fresh, cooked, or dried into powder with minimal nutrient loss and are widely used as nutritious food sources and animal feed. The leaves are rich in phytochemicals, such as phenolic acids, flavonoids, carotenoids, and glucosinolates, which contribute to their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and nutraceutical potential [10–12].

Table 3: Phytochemicals present in *Moringa Oleifera*

Phytochemical Class	Key Compounds	Therapeutic Effects	Sources
Flavonoids	Quercetin, Kaempferol	Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory	Leaves, Flowers
Phenolic Acids	Chlorogenic Acid	Antidiabetic, Cardioprotective	Leaves, Seeds
Glucosinolates	Glucoraphanin	Anticancer, Anti-inflammatory	Seeds, Pods
Saponins	Sapogenins	Antimicrobial, Cholesterol-lowering	Seeds
Vitamins and Minerals	Vitamins A, C, E; Calcium, Iron	Nutritional supplementation, Antioxidant	Leaves, Pods

Extraction Methods of *Moringa oleifera* Reported in Literature

Various studies have reported the preparation of ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *Moringa oleifera* leaves to evaluate their pharmacological potential. Ethanolic extraction methods are commonly employed to obtain flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and other bioactive constituents with antioxidant and enzyme-inhibitory properties [13].

Aqueous extraction methods, including decoction and boiling techniques, are widely reported in the literature and are traditionally used to prepare leaf extracts rich in water-soluble phytochemicals [14]. These extraction approaches influence the phytochemical profile, biological activity, and therapeutic efficacy of *Moringa oleifera* extracts, highlighting the importance of extraction method selection in phytopharmaceutical research.

Formulations of *Moringa Oleifera* Leaf Extract

Table 4: Formulations of *Moringa oleifera* Leaf Extract

Dosage Form	Route	Dose Range (Literature)	Active Phytochemicals	Bioavailability	Uses	References
Tablet	Oral	250–500 mg/tablet, 1–2 times daily	Quercetin, Kaempferol, Chlorogenic acid, Polyphenols	Moderate	Antioxidant, antidiabetic, antihyperlipidemic, anti-gout (xanthine oxidase inhibition), nutritional supplement	15
Capsule	Oral	400–1000 mg/day	Flavonoids, Phenolic acids, Isothiocyanates	Moderate	Immune support, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hyperuricemia/ gout management	16

Powder (Leaf / Extract Powder)	Oral	2–8 g/day leaf powder	Polyphenols, β -carotene, Iron, Proteins	Low–Moderate	Nutritional support, antioxidant, traditional use in gout and joint inflammation	17
Granules / Nutraceuticals	Oral	500–1500 mg/day	Total phenolics, Flavonoids	Moderate	Nutritional enhancement, antioxidant, supportive management of gout	18
Gel	Topical	2–10% w/w extract	Flavonoids, Tannins, Saponins	High (Local)	Anti-inflammatory, analgesic, relief of gout-associated joint inflammation, wound healing	19
Cream	Topical	2–5% w/w extract	Quercetin, Kaempferol, Vitamin E	Moderate–High (Local)	Anti-aging, antioxidant, joint pain and inflammation in gout	20
Lotion	Topical	1–5% w/w extract	Phenolic acids, Flavonoids	High (Local)	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, topical relief of gout symptoms	21
Nano-formulations	Oral / Topical	50–300 mg extract equivalent	Encapsulated quercetin, kaempferol	High	Enhanced antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, improved anti-gout potential via increased bioavailability	22
Hydrogel / Film Dressing	Topical	1–10% w/w extract	Flavonoids, Phenolics	High (Local)	Anti-inflammatory, analgesic, supportive relief in gout-related swelling, wound healing	23

CONCLUSION

Moringa oleifera leaf extract shows significant potential as a natural alternative for the management of gout. This effect is largely attributed to the rich content of bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, phenolic acids, and antioxidants. These phytochemicals exert multiple therapeutic actions, such as inhibiting xanthine oxidase to reduce uric acid production, regulating renal urate transporters to enhance uric acid excretion, and providing anti-inflammatory effects by modulating key pathways, including NF- κ B and cytokines (TNF- α and IL-6).

Various formulation strategies, such as tablets, capsules, powders, gels, creams, lotions, and advanced delivery systems, such as nano-

formulations and phytosomes, have been explored to improve bioavailability, stability, and therapeutic efficacy. Oral formulations mainly provide systemic effects, whereas topical formulations offer localized anti-inflammatory relief, which may be particularly useful during acute gout attacks. Advanced delivery systems, such as nano-formulations and phytosomes, enhance solubility, stability, and bioavailability, thereby maximizing therapeutic outcomes.

Overall, Moringa oleifera leaf extract offers a promising multi-mechanistic approach for gout management, combining uric acid-lowering and anti-inflammatory effects with potentially fewer side effects than conventional synthetic drugs. Future research should focus on clinical trials, standardization of extract composition, and

optimization of delivery systems to fully realize the therapeutic potential of this compound.

REFERENCES

1. Clebak KT, Morrison A, Croad JR. Gout: Rapid evidence review. *Am Fam Physician*. 2020;102(9):533-538.
2. Tumova S, Shi Y, Carr IM, Williamson G. Effects of quercetin and metabolites on uric acid biosynthesis and consequences for gene expression in the endothelium. *Free Radic Biol Med*. 2021;162:191-201. doi : 10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2020.10.017.
3. Kim Y, Oh HC, Park JW, et al. Diagnosis and treatment of inflammatory joint disease. *Hip Pelvis*. 2017;29(4):211-222. doi : 10.5371/hp.2017.29.4.211.
4. Roddy E. Revisiting the pathogenesis of podagra: why does gout target the foot? *J Foot Ankle Res*. 2011;4:13. doi : 10.1186/1757-1146-4-13.
5. Tripathi KD. *Essentials of Medical Pharmacology*. 8th ed. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers; 2018.
6. Tausche AK, Jansen TL, Schröder HE, Bornstein SR, Aringer M, Müller-Ladner U. Gout—current diagnosis and treatment. *Dtsch Arztebl Int*. 2009;106(34-35):549-555. doi : 10.3238/arztebl.2009.0549.
7. Al_husnan LA, Alkahtani MDF. Impact of Moringa aqueous extract on pathogenic bacteria and fungi in vitro. *Ann Agric Sci*. 2016;61(2):247-250. doi : 10.1016/j.aos.2016.06.003.
8. Falowo AB, Mukumbo FE, Idamokoro EM, Lorenzo JM, Afolayan AJ, Muchenje V. Multi-functional applications of Moringa oleifera Lam. in nutrition and animal food products: A review. *Food Res Int*. 2018;106:317-334. doi: 10.1016/j.foodres.2018.01.008.
9. Padayachee B, Baijnath H. An updated comprehensive review of the medicinal, phytochemical, and pharmacological properties of Moringa oleifera. *S Afr J Bot*. 2020;129:304-316. doi: 10.1016/j.sajb.2019.08.021.
10. Amaglo NK, Bennett RN, Lo Curto RB, Rosa EAS, Lo Turco V, Giuffrida A, et al. Profiling selected phytochemicals and nutrients in different tissues of the multipurpose tree Moringa oleifera L. grown in Ghana. *Food Chem*. 2010;122(4):1047-1054. doi: 10.1016/j.foodchem.2010.03.073.
11. Anwar F, Latif S, Ashraf M, Gilani AH. Moringa oleifera: a food plant with multiple medicinal applications. *2007;21(1):17-25*. doi: 10.1002/ptr.2023.
12. Borkar K, Argulwar G, Deshmukh S, Jaiswal S, Kitukale MD. Moringa Oleifera Tablets: A Comprehensive Review of Novel Formulation Techniques for Enhanced Bioavailability and Patient Compliance. *Int J Pharm Sci [Internet]*. 2025 Jan 22 [cited 2025 Dec 19];3(1):1825-38. Available from: www.ijpsjournal.com
13. Sermkaew N, Plyduang T. Self-microemulsifying drug delivery system of Moringa oleifera extract for enhanced dissolution of kaempferol and quercetin. *Acta Pharm*. 2020;70(1):77-88. doi: 10.2478/acph-2020-0012.
14. Palomino-Pacheco M, Rojas-Armas JP, Ortiz-Sánchez JM, Arroyo-Acevedo JL, Justil-Guerrero HJ, Martínez-Heredia JT. Assessment of oral toxicity of Moringa oleifera Lam aqueous extract and its effect on gout in a murine model. *Vet World*. 2024;17(7):1449-1458. doi: 10.14202/vetworld.2024.1449-1458.
15. Adebayo SA, Itiola OA, Ogunwuyi OJ. Design, formulation, and tableting properties

- of aqueous leaf extract of *Moringa oleifera* .
J Pharm Res Int. 2015;7(6):412–421.
16. Patil S, Patil P, Deshmukh R. Formulation and evaluation of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract capsules . *Res J Pharm Technol.* 2024;17(7):3125–3131.
17. Anwar F, Latif S, Ashraf M, Gilani AH. *Moringa oleifera* : a food plant with multiple medicinal uses. *Phytother Res.* 2007;21(1):17–25.
18. Kumar R, Patel DK, and Prasad SK. Development of nutraceutical granules containing *Moringa oleifera* . *Asian J Pharm.* 2019;13(3):245–251.
19. Sari DP, Rahmawati R, Putri NA. Gel formulation of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract (*Moringa oleifera* Lam.). *J Pharm Sci.* 2020;12(2):85–92.
20. Shrestha S, Shrestha J, Joshi S. Formulation and evaluation of cream using *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract. *J Inst Sci Technol.* 2022;27(1):45–52.
20. Shrestha S, Shrestha J, Joshi S. Formulation and evaluation of cream using *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract. *J Inst Sci Technol.* 2022;27(1):45–52.
21. Putri AR, Nugroho AK, Pramono S. Formulation of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract in lotion and gel as sunscreen. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Pharmaceutical Research* ; 2018. SCITEPRESS; p. 210–216.
22. Kumar N, Gupta P, Sharma V. Formulation, optimization , and evaluation of niosomes containing *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract *J Pharm Res Int.* 2021;33(45):123–132.
23. Mbikay M. Therapeutic potential of *Moringa oleifera* leaves in chronic hyperuricemia and inflammation: a review. *Front Pharmacol .* 2019;10:144

HOW TO CITE: Talele Urvasha, Kundhiya Sandhya, Patel Krishna, Patel Sakshi, Nagar Janvi, Falaq Jujara, Jaswandi Mehetre, Vimal Kumar, Therapeutic Potential of *Moringa* Extracts in Gout Management: A Comprehensive Review of Mechanisms, Formulations, and Future Prospects, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 1, 16-21. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18115498>